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Addressing National Spirit Through Rhetorical Analysis in Chairil Anwar's "Diponegoro" Poem

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Abstract

Chairil Anwar's poem Diponegoro is a literary work that is full of national spirit. This poem tells the story of Prince Diponegoro's struggle against the Dutch colonizers. Chairil Anwar uses various rhetorical techniques intelligently and effectively to arouse his readers' national spirit. This article aims to analyze the rhetoric used by Chairil Anwar in the poem "Diponegoro" to evoke the spirit of nationality. The author uses the text analysis method. Text analysis is a research method that intends to understand the meaning of the text in depth. The Diponegoro poem will be the focus of the text analysis in this study. Rhetorical analysis in the Diponegoro poem will reveal the deepest meaning of the poem through the description of the use of majas, sentence structure, and diction selection. According to the results of the research on Chairil Anwar's Diponegoro poem, there are various majas in it, such as personification, hyperbole, metaphor, synecdoke totem proparte, metonymia, oxymoron, and sarcasm. The choice of diction is the use of words that are firm and straightforward, the use of words that rhyme, and the use of words full of moral values.

Keyword: National spirit; Rhetorical analysis; Poem "Diponegoro"; Chairil Anwar

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INTRODUCTION

Research Problem

The national spirit is one of the important elements in building the nation's identity and self. This spirit is realized through various efforts, including literary works. Diponegoro's poem is an example of a literary work that is full of national spirit. Diponegoro's poem is clear evidence that literature can be a powerful tool to evoke national spirit. This work is not only highly aesthetic but also has educational and historical value that should be appreciated. Amidst the onslaught of modernization and globalization, this poem serves as a reminder to the younger generation about the importance of maintaining the spirit of nationalism and continuing to fight for the progress of the nation and state (Cristina, 2024; Munidar, 2024; Paull, 2024; Rahmadani, 2024; Johan, 2024; Ibrahi, 2024). Through rhetorical analysis, we can understand how Chairil Anwar builds national spirit in his poem (Akbar, 2023; Senen, 2024; Qamari; Andryrestu, 2024; Maisari, 2024). This analysis can help us better understand the relevance of Diponegoro's poetry to the current context. This research aims to analyze the rhetoric used by Chairil Anwar in the poem "Diponegoro" to evoke the spirit of nationality. This research uses the text analysis method.

Importance of Research for Field

This research is important for several reasons: rhetorical analysis helps dissect hidden meanings in poetry, revealing the message Chairil Anwar wants to convey about Diponegoro and his struggle against Dutch colonialism. It is important to understand the history of the nation and the role of heroes in liberating Indonesia. This research can foster appreciation for Indonesian literature, especially Chairil Anwar's works, and the history of the nation's struggle. By understanding the poem "Diponegoro," we can better appreciate the sacrifices of the heroes and their fighting spirit. The importance of this research is not only limited to the fields of literature and history but also has far-reaching implications in education, culture, and national identity. By researching the rhetoric of "Diponegoro," we can gain new insights into the meaning of the poem, Chairil Anwar's technique, and the national spirit contained in it. Researching the rhetoric of the poem "Diponegoro" is an important step toward understanding the nation's cultural heritage and fostering a sense of nationalism among the people.

Research or Theoretical Gap

Chairil Anwar's poem "Diponegoro" is one of the literary works that is full of meaning and evokes the spirit of nationality. This work has been analyzed from various perspectives, including rhetoric. However, there are still research gaps or theoretical gaps that need to be explored further. Theoretical gaps include: Lacking context analysis, most research only focuses on analyzing the text of the poem itself without paying attention to the context in which the poem was created. Understanding the historical and cultural context in which the poem was created can help readers understand the meaning of the poem better. Lack of reception analysis and research on rhetoric in the poem "Diponegoro" often ignores how the poem is received by readers. Reception analysis can help us understand how the poem affects readers and how readers interpret its meaning. Lacking intertextuality analysis, the poem "Diponegoro" has a relationship with other literary works, both Chairil Anwar's own works and the works of other writers. Intertextuality analysis can help us understand the poem's meaning more deeply and see how it interacts with other literary works.

Novelty of Research

This research offers novelty in several aspects. Rhetorical analysis approach: this research uses a comprehensive rhetorical analysis, combining analysis of linguistic structure, language style, and persuasion strategies. This approach allows for a deeper understanding of how Chairil Anwar constructs meaning and influence in his poetry. This research specifically focuses on how the poem "Diponegoro" evokes national spirit, focusing on national spirit. Chairil Anwar accomplishes this by scrutinizing his portrayal of Diponegoro as a hero, his battle against the invaders, and the patriotic values encapsulated in his poem. In the current context, this research connects the message of the poem "Diponegoro" to the current context, where the spirit of nationalism is still very relevant. The discussion focuses on how this poem can motivate the younger generation to contribute to the nation's progress. This research is expected to provide a new contribution to understanding Chairil Anwar's work and the role of poetry in fostering national spirit.

Research Objectives

This research aims to analyze Chairil Anwar's poem "Diponegoro," with a focus on rhetorical aspects, to understand how the spirit of nationality is represented and evoked in the poem. This research, in particular, will identify and analyze the language of thought, diction selection, and sentence structure used to build meaning and evoke the spirit of nationality. The poem "Diponegoro" holds significance in the present circumstances. We anticipate that this research will enhance our understanding of how literature shapes national identity and cultivates national spirit in Indonesia.

Research Question

1. How does the use of majas, diction, and sentence structure in "Diponegoro" contribute to the awakening of the national spirit?
2. What majas does Chairil Anwar use in the poem "Diponegoro" to build Diponegoro's image as a national hero and symbol of resistance to colonization?
3. How can the poem "Diponegoro" be relevant to the current context?

Role of Researchers

The role of the researcher in the article title "Addressing the Spirit of Nationalism Through Rhetorical Analysis in the Poem "Diponegoro" by Chairil Anwar" is as an observer. The researcher observes the poem "Diponegoro" by Chairil Anwar to identify the rhetorical elements contained in it. These rhetorical elements can take the form of thought patterns, language styles, sentence structures, and word choices. Analyzer: the researcher analyzes the rhetorical elements that have been identified to understand the meaning and purpose of the poem. Communicator: the researcher communicates the results of their analysis and interpretation to journal readers through clear, logical, and systematic writing. This writing must be able to convince readers of the validity and credibility of the research findings.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

In research articles, this section clearly outlines the perspective from which the research is conducted and the specific theories and key concepts underlying the research.

Image

A language of thought is a style of language that is useful for giving allusions (certain meanings) to a sentence. The use of language of thought is intended to beautify, enrich, and emphasize the meaning of a literary work, such as poetry, prose, or speech. According to KBBI (Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia), language of thought is a way of expressing thoughts or feelings indirectly using figurative words. Gorys Keraf says that language of thought is the use of unusual or unusual language with the aim of obtaining certain effects in literary works.

Sentence Structure

Chairil Anwar, in his poem "Diponegoro," uses various sentence structures to create certain meanings and nuances. Here are some of the analyses:

- a. Direct and Indirect Sentences
- b. Imperative Sentence
- c. Compound Sentences

Diction Selection

Chairil Anwar's poem Diponegoro is a literary work that is full of meaning and evokes the spirit of nationality. The choice of diction in this poem is a crucial aspect to study. Through a careful choice of words, Chairil Anwar succeeded in portraying Diponegoro as a brave leader who persevered against the invaders and aroused the spirit of his readers to fight for independence.

- a. Use of Strong and Straightforward Words
- b. Use of Rhyming Words
- c. Use of Moral Words

METHOD

Research Design

The researcher used text analysis and a qualitative approach to complete this study. Text Analysis Method, Text analysis is a research method that aims to understand the text's meaning in depth. In this study, the text analysis will focus on the poem "Diponegoro" by Chairil Anwar.

Qualitative Approach, A qualitative approach is one that focuses on the meaning and deep understanding of a phenomenon. We will use a qualitative approach in this research to understand how the poem "Diponegoro" evokes the spirit of nationality through rhetoric. We will implement the qualitative approach through multiple stages or procedures.

Data Sources

The source of data for the purpose of this research is journal articles, research reports, and official documents related to the Diponegoro Poem and its rhetorical analysis.

Data Collection and Procedure

1. Data collection by analyzing the text of the poem "Diponegoro".
2. Analyzing the data systematically and deeply.
3. Interpreting the meaning and findings of the data analysis.
4. Draw conclusions about how the rhetoric in the poem "Diponegoro" evokes the national spirit.

Data Analysis

The analysis of the Spirit of Nationalism through Rhetoric in the Poem "Diponegoro" by Chairil Anwar employs a qualitative approach. Text Analysis Method: The analysis of the poem "Diponegoro" by Chairil Anwar uses a text analysis method with a qualitative approach. This is done by: reading the poem repeatedly to understand its meaning and context thoroughly; identifying the rhetorical elements used; analyzing the meaning and function of the rhetorical elements in building the spirit of nationality; and drawing conclusions about how the rhetoric in this poem evokes the reader's spirit of nationality.

Accuracy

Precision in the qualitative approach of the text analysis method is crucial to producing valid and credible research findings. Here are some important aspects that need to be considered to ensure accuracy in qualitative text analysis:

1. Mature Research Design
2. Proficient Researcher Skills
3. Data Validity and Reliability
4. Clarity and Consistency of Interpretation
5. Research Ethics

It is important to remember that accuracy in qualitative text analysis is contextual and depends on the research purpose, the type of text data, and the researcher's expertise. No one method or technique can guarantee absolute accuracy. However, by applying the aforementioned principles and following good research ethics guidelines, researchers can increase the credibility and validity of their research findings.

Trustworthiness

Using qualitative text analysis methods can provide richness and depth of meaning. Qualitative text analysis enables researchers to delve into a text's deeper meaning. This method reveals complex nuances and contexts without relying on numbers. Flexibility: Rigid rules do not bind qualitative text analysis. Researchers can develop analytical approaches and techniques that align with the text's research objectives and characteristics. Ability to Reveal New Things: This method can uncover unexpected patterns and themes, opening up new insights into a phenomenon.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Findings

Attached is the poem Diponegoro by Chairil Anwar;

Diponegoro

(Chairil Anwar's work)

In this time of development

Tuan comes back to life

And the embers of admiration become fire

In front of you once awaits
Unafraid of a hundred times the number of opponents
Sword on the right and dagger on the left
a spirit that cannot die
FORWARD
This is a line without a hammer
Trust is a sign of storming
Once means once
After that it dies
FORWARD
For you the land Provides fire
Extinct above servitude
Perish above being oppressed
Truly the path of death is only reached
If life must feel
Forward
Attack
Attack
Strike

The Diponegoro poem is a poem that discusses the difficulties, tribulations, and moral lessons that can be learned from the experience of a nation and the struggle and spirit of a hero and the Indonesian nation when trying to defend themselves from those who enslaved them at that time.

Rhetorical analysis

The rhetorical analysis in the poem "Diponegoro" will reveal the poem's deepest meaning through the description of the language of thought, sentence structure, and diction selection. The language of thought is used to strengthen the description of Prince Diponegoro's struggle and arouse the reader's national spirit.

Language of Thought

A language of thought is a style of language that is useful for giving allusions (certain meanings) to a sentence. The use of language of thought is intended to beautify, enrich, and emphasize the meaning of a literary work, such as poetry, prose, or speech. According to KBBI (Kamus Besar Bahasa Indonesia), language of thought is a way of expressing thoughts or feelings indirectly using figurative words. Gorys Keraf says that language of thought is the use of unusual or unusual language with the aim of obtaining certain effects in literary works.

D.S. Prawiroharjo said that language of thought is a way of expressing ideas and feelings using figurative words with the aim of creating a certain effect. According to Slamet Muljana, language of thought means choosing words and arranging them beautifully for the feelings that arise in the writer, then creating certain conditions in the reader. Aminudin adds that language of thought is a style of language that is useful for stringing sentences so that they are able to

describe or represent thoughts based on existing ideas or norms. From the various explanations that researchers have conveyed, it comes to the conclusion that language of thought is the use of unusual language used to produce certain effects and aims to beautify, enrich, and emphasize the meaning of a literary work.

Discussion

Personification

Personification is a language style that treats inanimate objects as humans, or considers humans to be inanimate objects (Maryatim, 2018). The KBBI clarifies that personification is a language style that represents inanimate objects as if they were human (alive). According to Gorys Keraf, personification is a language style that anthropomorphizes inanimate objects, namely giving human characteristics and behavior to inanimate objects. The language of thought used in Diponegoro's poem, namely:

In this time of development

Tuan lives

The poet wants the burning spirit of all Indonesian people to free themselves from colonialism. The fragment of the poem contains the meaning of the term "tuan," which in this case is not the meaning of "a hero named Diponegoro" but refers to the meaning of "spirit" that is present in Indonesian society. It is evident that the poem's fragment employs a personification technique, characterizing humans (tuan) as inanimate entities (spirits). The word spirit contains meaning, namely the essence of strength or endurance to fight. The word spirit has an abstract or intangible nature.

Metaphorical Language of thought

Marthatiana (2020) and Wahab said that metaphor is an expression of language with a meaning that cannot be expressed clearly (implicitly) from the language symbolism used in the formation of sentences, but readers can infer and understand it. Through the poem, the metaphor is:

Sword on the right dagger on the left

The poem fragment indicates that there will be many reinforcements when the Indonesian people unite in defending the nation. The phrase "sword on the right" does not refer to a spear or any other type of sharp weapon. The phrase "keris on the left" does not convey the idea that when facing a crisis, Indonesians would use a sharp weapon similar to a keris. The term "keris" in this verse contains a clue that wealth comes from the "khalik" or "empunya" in everyday life because, at that time, there were still people who believed in mystical powers. From the explanation above, it is clear that the poem uses metaphorical language of thought because it contains an implicit impression or does not convey the real meaning.

Hyperbole

Hyperbole is a language style that exaggerates with the aim of emphasizing or excluding the object being described as looking greater (Fellani, 2022). The poem by Diponegoro, which uses hyperbole, can be found here:

And the embers of awe become fire

The fragment of the poem above means that the poet is conveying admiration for Prince Diponegoro. KBBI clarifies bara as charcoal that has been burned. Just as his admiration for Prince Diponegoro was admired with the usual impression, after his persistence and courage to defend the Indonesian nation, the poet admires even more as if it were a fire. Hence his courage and persistence in defending the Indonesian nation. Tarigan (2013) states that hyperbole is a language style to convey something by exaggerating it, both in quantity, size and nature. Thus, the author concludes that hyperbole is a sentence or expresses something with something that can clearly simplify it.

Metonymy

Parera, in Hidayat (2022), asserted that metonymy serves as a crucial tool for elucidating a concept by drawing a comparison with an object or activity that shares similar attributes, and

establishing a connection between the two elements. Diponegoro's poem contains elements of metonymy, namely.

This is a line that does not flutter

hammered Trust sign invades

This description implies that the Indonesian people do not carry weapons or are ready to fight with their bare hands. The Indonesian nation is actively working to reclaim the homeland that the colonizers had stolen. In the KBBI, "genderang" refers to a drum, which is then used as a tool to start a war, a tool, or a sensor for beating. As per this piece of poetry, the term "hammer" has nothing to do with the actual meaning of a hammer but rather a sharp weapon or weapon of war. Based on the description above, it is clear that this piece of poetry utilizes metaphor, which is evident through the terms "drum and hammer," which are accurately used for weapons of war.

Oxymoron

Oxymoron is a language style that contains opposition by embedding incompatible or opposite diction in a sentence (Jayantini, 2018). Diponegoro's poem with oxymoron, namely:

Once means

Already it is dead

In accordance with this description, it conveys the idea that all Indonesian people are willing to do or sacrifice whatever they have to have anything. This includes death. The poet describes whether giving the best service before dying on the battlefield is the goal of the Indonesian people. The explanation reveals that the poem employs an oxymoron, as it juxtaposes the definitions of "means" or "sacrifice" and "die" or "death" in two lines.

Sarcasm

Sarcasm refers to a type of grammar that focuses on certain words, such as mockery or ridicule, satire, scathing words, and so on (Wahyuni, 2022). This sarcasm gives a depiction of bitterness and sadness and can offend someone. Diponegoro's poem contains elements of sarcasm, namely:

Extinct on seroitude

Perish on being oppressed

The poet describes the meaning of the poem above, saying that the Indonesian people have made sacrifices to the point of blood loss. The Indonesian people are also fearless in expending all their strength until they have no choice but to defend the nation. The sarcastic terms can be found in "perish" and "oppressed." "Perish" implies destruction, while "oppressed" signifies exploitation.

Totem proparte synecdoche

The synecdoche totem proparte is a figure of speech that describes all the smaller things as representations of something large or general (Wulandari, 2022). The fragment contains Diponegoro's poem that utilizes the synecdoche totem proparte.

In front once the master awaits

According to this description, it contains the meaning of truth if the Indonesian people are willing to wholeheartedly defend their nation and have a persistent will to get rid of everything related to colonialism in the country. The term "lord" does not refer to one person but to the entire Indonesian population at that time. According to the explanation above, it gives an understanding of whether the language of thought in this particular poem is the language of thought synecdoche totem proparte.

Sentence Structure

Chairil Anwar in his poem "Diponegoro" uses various sentence structures to create certain meaning and nuance effects. Here are some of the analyses:

1. Direct and Indirect Sentences

As in the first and second stanzas, direct sentences present Diponegoro's voice directly. This builds a heroic and brave impression of Diponegoro. In this time of development, the Lord comes back to life, and admiring embers become fire. The third and fourth stanzas use indirect sentences to describe the situation and conditions surrounding Diponegoro. This use provides context and background to Diponegoro's struggle. In front of you once, the master waited. Undaunted. Opponents are a hundred times as numerous.

2. Imperative Sentence

It is used to give orders or invitations, such as in the first stanza, "In this time of development, you are alive again." This sentence evokes the spirit and determination to fight the colonizers. Declarative sentences are used to convey statements, as in the second stanza, and admiring embers become fire. This sentence emphasizes Prince Diponegoro's determination and conviction in his struggle.

3. Compound Sentence

Used to combine two ideas or clauses into one sentence, as in the first stanza, In this time of development, the Lord comes back to life, and admiring embers become fire. These compound sentences make the poem more complex and rich in meaning. Simplified sentences are used to convey a single idea in a short and concise manner, as in the second stanza, Undaunted. The opponent is a hundred times. These simple sentences give a firm and straightforward impression.

Diction Selection

Chairil Anwar's poem Diponegoro is a literary work that is full of meaning and evokes the spirit of nationality. The choice of diction in this poem is one aspect worth examining. Through a careful choice of words, Chairil Anwar succeeded in portraying Diponegoro as a brave leader who persevered against the colonizers and aroused the spirit of his readers to fight for independence.

1. Use of Strong and Straightforward Words

Chairil Anwar uses many strong and straightforward words in this poem. Words like "fight," "hit," and "destroy" clearly show the determination of Diponegoro and his people to defeat the invaders. This word choice is also effective in evoking the fighting spirit of his readers.

Example:

- In this time of development, Tuan lives again
- And the embers of awe become fire
- Undaunted. Opponents a hundred times over
- Clad in a spirit that cannot die.
- Forward.

The use of the words "undaunted" and "forward" shows Diponegoro's courage and determination to continue fighting, despite having to face much stronger opponents. The word sash with a spirit that cannot die shows that Diponegoro's fighting power will never die and will continue to inspire the next generation to fight for independence.

2. Use of Rhyming Words

Chairil Anwar also uses rhyming words in this poem. The use of rhyme creates a musical effect and makes it easier for readers to memorize. This also strengthens the message that the poet wants to convey.

For example:

- It's a row of no-hammered lines
- The belief of the sign invades
- Extinct above servitude
- Perish upon oppression

This stanza's use of rhyme makes the poem easier to remember and recite. This can also help spread the message of Diponegoro and his people's struggle to a larger community.

3. Use of Moral Words

In addition to strict and straightforward words, Chairil Anwar also uses words that contain moral values in this poem. Words like "justice," "freedom," and "independence" show the noble ideals of Diponegoro and his people.

Example:

- Where the foot treads the land of his blood
- That's where I build from however lowly it is

The use of the phrase "the land of his blood" demonstrates Diponegoro's love for his homeland. The words "no matter how low" show Diponegoro's determination to rise up and fight for independence, despite having to face various obstacles and barriers. The careful choice of diction in Diponegoro's poetry is an important factor that makes this literary work so memorable and evokes the spirit of nationalism. Through the right choice of words, Chairil Anwar succeeded in portraying Diponegoro as a brave leader who persevered against oppression and aroused the spirit of his readers to fight for independence. This poem also proves that literature can be an effective tool to convey moral messages and raise the nation's fighting spirit.

The Relevance of Diponegoro's Poem to the Present Context

Diponegoro's poem is the most famous and inspiring work of Indonesian literature. This poem tells the story of Prince Diponegoro's struggle against the Dutch colonizers in the 19th century. This poem retains its relevance in the current context, where the Indonesian nation continues to confront various challenges. Relevance of the Diponegoro Poem to the Current Context:

1. Fighting Spirit and Never Give Up

In this poem, Diponegoro is portrayed as a brave, unyielding figure who has a strong determination to fight the invaders. This spirit is very relevant to the current context, where the Indonesian people are still struggling to achieve complete independence. We must continue to confront challenges like poverty, social inequality, and corruption. Diponegoro's fight and unyielding spirit can inspire the younger generation to keep fighting to advance the country.

2. Unity and Unity

In his poetry, Diponegoro often emphasizes the important role of national unity in fighting any kind of colonization. This is also relevant to the current context, where the Indonesian people must unite to face various challenges. Respecting differences, fostering tolerance, and fostering mutual cooperation can lead to unity.

3. Love of the Motherland

Diponegoro has a love for the country. It can be seen in his strong determination to fight the invaders and liberate his homeland. Today's younger generation must also embody this love for the country. Loving the country will inspire the younger generation to strive for the nation's betterment. Chairil Anwar's poem "Diponegoro" is a valuable source of inspiration for the Indonesian people. The spirit of nationality, unity, integrity, and love for the country must continue to be instilled in the younger generation. With this spirit and values, the Indonesian nation can continue to progress and achieve the ideals of independence.

Research Significance

This research has several important significances, both in the academic and national contexts national context:

1. **Academic Contribution:** Enriching the understanding of Chairil Anwar's "Diponegoro" poem through in-depth rhetorical analysis. Providing new insights into how Chairil Anwar used language and rhetorical techniques to evoke the spirit of nationality. Increase appreciation of Indonesian literature, especially Chairil Anwar's poetry. Enrich the academic discourse on literature and nationalism in Indonesia.
2. **Nationality Contribution:** Strengthen people's understanding of the meaning and values contained in the poem "Diponegoro". Raising the spirit of nationality and love for the country

among the community. Increase public awareness of the importance of the independence struggle and the role of national heroes. Encourage the community to play an active role in nation building.

3. Originality and Novelty: This research has never been done before with a focus on rhetorical analysis in the poem "Diponegoro". This makes this research original and innovative.

CONCLUSION

Diponegoro is a poem that is full of national spirit. This can be seen in the use of strong and effective rhetoric, such as language of thought, sentence structure, and diction selection. This poem's national spirit can inspire every generation to keep fighting to advance the Indonesian nation. The poem "Diponegoro" has high relevance to the current context and can be a source of inspiration for the Indonesian people to remain united and fight to advance the nation and state. According to the analysis carried out on Chairil Anwar's Diponegoro poem, it contains the language of thought used, such as personification, hyperbole, metaphor, synecdoke totem proparte, metonimia, oxymoron, and sarcasm. The choice of diction includes, among others, the use of words that are firm and straightforward, the use of words that rhyme, and the use of words that contain moral values.

Recommendation for Future Research

The author aspires to enhance research both internally and externally. The author hopes that future research will conduct similar research by exploring issues that have not been studied in the current study.

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DECLARATION OF CONFLICTING INTERESTS

The authors expressly declare that there is no potential conflict of interest between the research, authorship, or publication of this article. We conduct all research and writing objectively and transparently, free from any influence that could sway the results or interpretation of the research findings.

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